

Fungicide timing to control rice sheath blight (ShB)

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We tested control of ShB caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* by carbendazim and mancozeb applied at different crop growth and disease development stages during 1987 and 1938 pishanam. Plot size was 5 × 4.5 m, plant spacing 20 × 10 cm, in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fertilizer was applied at 120-162.5-147.5 kg NPK/ha (Ec 0.16, pH 5.8). IR8 was transplanted 30 d after seeding (DAS) on 11 Nov 1987 and 12 Dec 1988.

Fungicides were applied when

Effect of time of application and rate of fungicide for control of rice ShB. Ambasamudram, India, 1987-88.

Fungicide	Time of application	ShB grade	Yield (t/ha)
Mancozeb 1000 g/ha	Disease grade 1	3.6	4.2
Mancozeb 1000 g/ha	Disease grade 3	4.9	4.2
Mancozeb 1000 g/ha	Disease grade 5	5.8	4.1
Carbendazim 250 g/ha	Disease grade 1	3.6	4.2
Carbendazim 250 g/ha	Disease grade 3	5.0	4.2
Carbendazim 250 g/ha	Disease grade 5	5.7	4.1
Carbendazim 250 g/ha	At panicle initiation and heading	2.8	4.3
Mancozeb	At panicle initiation and heading	3.3	4.3
Carbendazim	At heading	3.5	4.2
Mancozeb	At heading	3.4	4.2
No fungicide	—	6.0	4.2
LSD		1.4	ns

disease severity was 1, 3, and 5 and at panicle initiation (PI) (65 DAS) or at heading (80 DAS), or both. Both fungicides sprayed at grade 1 disease stage controlled the disease at grade 3.6 (see table). Spraying at grade 3 or 5 did

not prevent the disease from developing to higher levels. Carbendazim and mancozeb sprayed at PI and 15 d after PI also controlled disease development. Yield differences were not significant. □

Influence of rice plant density and spacing on brown leaf spot incidence

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We studied the influence of seedlings/hill and spacings between hills on brown leaf spot disease Jan-Mar 1989.

Rice cultivar ASD16 was transplanted at one and two seedlings/hill and three spacings in 4- × 5-m plots, in randomized factorial block design with six replications. Normal fertilizer schedule of 100 kg N/ha as urea, 50 kg P/ha as superphosphate, and 50 kg K/ha as potash was applied as basal and topdressing. No fungicide

Influence of plant density (1 or 2 seedlings/hill) and spacing on brown leaf spot incidence in rice. Coimbatore, India, Jan-Mar 1989.

Spacing (cm)	Disease incidence (%)					
	30 d after transplanting			50 d after transplanting		
	1	2	Mean	1	2	Mean
10 × 10	35.56	39.31	37.44	43.19	44.95	44.07
10 × 15	31.61	34.69	33.15	38.57	40.63	39.60
10 × 20	26.17	27.84	27.01	35.20	35.27	35.24
Mean	31.11	33.95	—	38.98	40.29	—
LSD (0.05)						
Seedlings/hill	ns	ns				
Spacing	3.89	4.11				
Interaction	ns	ns				

was applied. Brown leaf spot incidence was assessed at 30 and 50 d after transplanting.

Plots with closer spacing (10 × 10

cm) had significantly higher disease incidence than wider spacing at both density levels and at both observation times (see table). □

Effect of N on false smut (FS) in upland rice

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We studied the effect of N level on FS

caused by *Ustilaginoidea virens* in rainfed rice. The experiment was conducted during 1987 wet season using rice variety Himalaya 741 (CR125-42-5/IR2061-213) at Malan.

Two sources of N, two N levels, and three application schedules were compared with farmer's practice, in randomized block design with three

replications. False-smutted panicles and healthy panicles in 3 random hill samples and false-smutted florets on 30 random panicles were counted in each treatment.

Higher N levels in split applications resulted in higher number of smutted florets/m² (see table). There were no significant differences in